

equilibria. From these formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by the half integral method. Since the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values for Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , was found to be less than 1.78 log units, the same were calculated by least square method. The standard deviation of $\log K$ values was calculated by the standard method⁵ and was found to be 0.02. The limits of error were also calculated⁵ and were found to be ± 0.02 .

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of the trivalent metal chelates was found to be

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

$t = 25^\circ$		$\mu = 0.1$					
Cations	H^+	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	La^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Y^{3+}
$\log K_1$	7.97	8.11	7.9	7.65	7.08	6.02	4.8
$\log K_2$	—	5.98	—	—	5.18	—	3.8

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 corresponds to the species LH , while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 , respectively.

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Studies on the Complexes of Platinum Group Metals with Nicotinamide and Brucine

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THE present communication reports the complex formation of platinum group metals with nicotinamide and brucine which finds little mention in the existing chemical literature.

Experimental

Na_2PtCl_4 , Na_2PdCl_4 , Na_2OsCl_6 , Na_2IrCl_6 and $RhCl_3 \cdot H_2O$ (Johnson Matthey), nicotinamide (B.D.H) and brucine (Whiffen) were used in these experiments.

The metal-nicotinamide (or metal-brucine) complexes were prepared by mixing the ethanolic solutions of the metal salt and the ligand with vigorous shaking when a precipitate was obtained. It was washed several times with ethanol and subsequently with hexane and then dried *in vacuo*. The complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents making their crystallization impossible.

The complexes were microanalysed for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and chlorine. The hydrogen analyses are somewhat high because of the ready absorption of water by these complexes during the process of analysis. The molar conductance was measured on a Philips conductivity bridge model PR 9500 in dimethyl sulphoxide using $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions Table 1.

The infra red spectra of the complexes were recorded on a 'Perkin-Elmer' model '621' ir machine in the frequency range of $4000-600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in KBr pellets. The magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Faraday balance at B.H.U., Varanasi. The thermograms were run on a manual apparatus at G. N. D. University, Amritsar and the diffused transmittance spectra were taken in nujol mull on NIR-vis-DMR-21 apparatus at RSIC, Madras.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis of the complexes shows that Pd(II) and Pt(II) interact with nicotinamide to give complexes with the composition, $Pd(\text{Nicotinamide})_2Cl_2$ and $Pt(\text{Nicotinamide})_2Cl_2$. The molar conductance¹ shows that they are non-electrolytes.

Nicotinamide absorbs at 3360, 3160 (NH bands), 1670 (CO stretching), 1610 and 1595 (C=C and C=N stretchings), 1115 (ν_{CN}) and at 1020 and 696 cm^{-1} (pyridine ring vibrations). The CO frequency goes down by $10-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation. The $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ go to 1600, 1586, 1585 and 1525 cm^{-1} in Pd and Pt complexes respectively. The pyridine ring vibrations occur at 1020 and 682 ; and at 1000 and 640 cm^{-1} in Pd and Pt complexes respectively and show a great decrease in intensity. The NH bands at 3360 and 3160 cm^{-1} show splitting into several peaks in the two complexes. These changes in the ir absorptions show that the coordination of platinum and palladium occurs through the oxygen of the carbonyl group and the heterocyclic nitrogen. Thus both palladium and platinum are hexacoordinated in these complexes with nicotinamide.

The alkaloid, brucine forms 1 : 1 complexes with Pd(II), Pt(II), Os(IV) and Ir(IV) chlorides. $RhCl_3$ forms a 2 : 1 complex. The complexes are

TABLE 1—RESULT OF ANALYSES

Metal-nicotinamide complexes Molecular formula	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	%C	%H	%N	%Cl	Δm in ohm^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$
1. $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N.CONH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	Yellow	340	84.68 *(34.19)	3.00 (2.87)	13.17 (13.29)	16.31 (16.82)	8.2
2. $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N.CONH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	Light pink	320	28.00 (28.25)	2.86 (2.37)	10.54 (10.89)	14.5 (13.90)	6.8
<i>Metal-brucine complexes</i>							
1. $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_2$	Black	215	48.91 (48.32)	5.01 (4.58)	4.93 (4.90)	11.95 (12.40)	18.1
2. $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_2$	Light pink	270	42.80 (41.88)	4.32 (3.96)	4.20 (4.24)	10.94 (10.74)	34.0
3. $\text{Os}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_4$	Black	above 360	38.00 (38.03)	4.21 (3.61)	3.74 (3.86)	19.96 (19.52)	36.6
4. $\text{Ir}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_4$	Dirty white	"	35.97 (37.92)	3.88 (3.60)	3.81 (3.85)	20.03 (19.47)	27.6
5. $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_4$	Reddish brown	"	34.45 (33.98)	3.80 (3.22)	3.42 (3.45)	25.74 (26.16)	17.0

* Calculated values are given in parentheses.

insoluble in water and common organic solvents but slightly soluble in DMF and THF. The molar conductivity measurements carried out in DMSO indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The ir spectrum of brucine shows two bands at 1655 and 1395 cm^{-1} , which are respectively assigned to CO and CN stretching vibrations of the acylazole system³. The CO stretching band is lowered by 10 to 20 cm^{-1} in the complexes and it favours the possibility of coordination through oxygen of the carbonyl group. The strong intensity band at 1115 cm^{-1} in the brucine has been assigned to CO stretching of the seven membered cyclic ether^{3,4}, which shows a slight lowering of frequency in all the complexes except Rh(III) complex where the lowering is quite marked. It is therefore assumed that the second Rh atom coordinates through this oxygen.

On the basis of the ir evidence it may be inferred that Pt(II), Pd(II), Os(IV), Rh(III) and Ir(IV) coordinate through the carbonyl groups of the acylazole ring. The complexes of iridium and rhodium with brucine are found to be diamagnetic.

The thermogram of palladium nicotinamide complex shows a wt. loss of 10.0% at 200° which may be the elimination of CONH₂ group (theo. wt. loss is 10.44%). A break in the curve occurs at 30.0% wt. loss at 356°. This may be the elimination of C₆H₄N of the nicotinamide and from which CONH₂ was given off (theo. wt. loss=28.95%). After this, there is a continuous weight loss which may entail the elimination of the second molecule of nicotinamide, sublimation of complex species and the removal of the chloride ions. The weight becomes constant at 81.0% wt. loss at 460° which is more than that calculated for the formation of metallic palladium (74.75%).

The thermogram of platinum brucine complex shows an inflection point at 20.0% wt. loss and 160-200° temperature. This may be due to the elimination of the two OCH₃ groups and the (CH₂)₃N

which accounts for 17.86% wt. loss. The maximum weight loss is 73.0% at 380°, which accounts for the formation of metallic platinum (theo. wt. loss=70.44%). The rhodium complex shows inflection points at 280 and 400° with wt. losses of 52.0% (theo. wt. loss for the formation of 2 RhCl₃=48.47%) and 80.0% (theo. wt. loss for the formation of 2 Rh=87.34%). These thermograms indicate the removal of two methoxy groups and the CH₂-CH₂-N-CH₂ of the aliphatic pyrrocoline ring at low temperatures when nothing else is eliminated. This may mean the non-coordination of the metal ion with this nitrogen in all these complexes as also evidenced by ir spectra.

The electronic spectra of Ir (Brucine) Cl₄ shows bands at 17391, 20833 and 25000 cm^{-1} . This may have a pentacoordinate square pyramidal structure and the first and the last band may be due to $d_{z^2} \leftarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xz}/d_{yz} \leftarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions.

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Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Complexes at Different Ionic Strengths

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THE role of electrolytes on the dissociation constants of ligands and their complexes are not well-understood. The dissociation constants are